

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It is a great pleasure to announce the third regular issue of 2019. I'd like to thank all authors for contributing their sound research and the editorial board for the highly valuable review effort and comments for improvements. These contributions together with the generous support of the consortium members sustains the quality of our journal.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce five accepted papers from five different countries.

Vladimir M. Ciric, Ivan Z. Milentijevic, Oliver M. Vojinovic, and Nemanja S. Manic from Serbia present in their paper technical requirements and a mathematical model which allows to estimate the cost of course delivery through public cloud. Rogério C. P. Fragoso, Roberto H. W. Pinheiro, and George D. C. Cavalcanti from Brazil focus on data-driven feature selection methods for text classification, more specifically on the evaluation of dimensionality reduction, classification performance and execution time of selected methods. Asieh Ghanbarpour and Hassan Naderi from Iran conduct a survey on ranking functions in keyword search over graph-structured data. Matías Micheletto, Rodrigo Santos, and Javier Orozco from Argentina present in their paper meta-heuristics to solve the energy aware reward based scheduling of real-time tasks with mandatory and optional parts in homogeneous multi-core processors. Zeynep Banu Ozger, Bulent Bolat and Banu Diri from Turkey propose in their research a hybrid gene selection method for discriminatively selecting genes based on the probabilistic binary Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm PrBABC, which is hybridized with three different filter methods.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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